

EVALUATION INDICATORS OF INVESTMENT PROJECTS IMPLEMENTED ON THE BASIS OF PUBLIC-PRIVATE PARTNERSHIP

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Annotation: Throughout this article evaluation indicators of investment projects implemented on the basis of public-private partnership may differ depending on the specific project and its goals given. However, some common evaluation indicators include: Financial sustainability, Risk assessment, Economic and social impact, Environmental impact, Technical feasibility, Legal and regulatory compliance. By evaluating investment projects based on these indicators, stakeholders can make informed decisions about how best to structure a PPP arrangement to ensure that the project continues or succeeds.

Key words: Evaluation indicators, PPP, investment projects, Coverage period, Investment return index, Discount rate.

The evaluation of investment projects for the development of transport infrastructure under the conditions of public-private partnership should be carried out on the basis of a comprehensive analysis of economic, social and environmental indicators. The main economic indicators of such projects are indicators of economic efficiency of investment projects, which combine capital and operating costs for the entire life cycle of projects.

The main criterion for the selection of investment projects at the World Bank is the discounted modern value of benefits after excluding costs. Both revenues and costs will increase during the implementation of the project. In order for the project to pass the economic competition, it must comply with the following two conditions: - the net modern value of the profit expected from the implementation of the project must not be negative; - the expected net present value of the project should be equal to or higher than the expected net present value of alternative conflicting projects. Financial evaluation is used in the analysis of

liquidity during the implementation of the investment project. In other words, the task of financial assessment is to determine whether the enterprise will have sufficient financial resources to fulfill its total financial obligations in order to implement the project within the specified time. Economic assessment is used to determine the potential ability of an investment project, to maintain the value of the funds invested in this project and to create a sufficient level of their growth rate.

The entire set of indicators for evaluating the efficiency of an investment project can be divided into 2 groups¹.

1. Static indicators that ignore the theory of the time value of money:

- net income (NI);
- ordinary payment period (PP);
- profitability index (PI);
- accounting rate of return on investments (ARR).

2. Dynamic - based on the theory of the time value of money and the mechanism of discounting cash flows:

- net present value (NPV);
- discounted payment term (PB (DPP));
- discounted profitability index (DPI);
- internal rate of return (IRR).

Let's take a closer look at the listed statistical methods:

1. Net income - reflecting the efficiency of project implementation in absolute terms (value) for participants:

$$NV = \sum_{t=1}^T CF_t - \sum_{t=1}^T I_t$$

Here

CF_t - t amount of net cash flows created by the project at the calculation stage;

¹ Борисова О.В. Инвестиции в 2 т. Т. 2. Инвестиционный менеджмент: учебник и практикум для бакалавриата и магистратуры. Москва: Издательство Юрайт, 2019. - С. 134

I_t - t volume of investment costs for the calculation stage;

T - total duration of the project implementation project (number of years).

A value of $NV > 0$ implies the project's efficiency and payback over the project's life cycle time frame.

Obviously, the higher the value of NV , the higher the efficiency of the project. And accordingly, when evaluating the effectiveness of several alternative projects, the project characterized by a high level of net income will be more attractive to the investor.

2. Normal payback period (PP) is an indicator that describes the minimum period of time during which the funds invested in the project will return.

If the investments in the project are of a one-time nature, the payback period can be determined by the ratio of investment costs (I_0) and average annual net cash flows:

$$PP = \frac{I_0}{\sum_{t=1}^T CF_t / T}$$

If capital investments are distributed over time, then it can be determined by interrelating the total amount of expenses and the total amount of net cash flows generated by the project and multiplying this ratio by the number of years in the accounting period:

$$PP = \frac{\sum_{t=1}^T I_t}{\sum_{t=1}^T CF_t} \times T$$

The most accurate calculation of the payback period is given by the method of direct calculation of the number of years in which the investment will be paid back by the income generated by the project. This method consists of three steps²

a) determine the total number of years in which the amount of cash receipts will be as close as possible to the amount of the investment;

² Тухтамурадов И.Б. Особенности и методы оценки инвестиционных проектов // Проблемы внедрения результатов инновационных разработок. Сборник статей международной научно-практической конференции: в 3 частях, 2017. – С.6

b) determining the outstanding balance as the difference between the volume of investments and the volume of net cash receipts;

c) the outstanding balance is divided into net cash receipts of the next period.

Despite the relatively high labor intensity, this method gives the most accurate result, because it allows you to take into account possible uneven investment costs and cash receipts over the years.

Regardless of which method is used, it is important to remember when calculating the repayment period³:

If $PP < T$, then the project should be accepted;

If $PP > T$, then it is necessary to reject the project or revise the initial parameters of the project (investments, income, costs, implementation periods);

If $PP = T$, then the project is neither profitable nor unprofitable.

3. Investment profitability index - an indicator describing the level of profitability of a unit of funds invested in a project in the form of net income:

$$PI = \frac{\sum_{t=1}^T CF_t}{\sum_{t=1}^T I_t} \times T$$

If $PI > 1$, then the project should be accepted;

If $PI < 1$, then it is necessary to reject the project or revise the initial parameters of the project (investments, income, costs, implementation period);

If $PI = 1$, then the project has zero efficiency.

4. The accounting norm of investment profitability is the ratio of the average annual value of net cash flows from operating activities to the average value of investments.

If the project envisages the write-off of all investment costs after the end of its implementation period, the average annual volume of investments is calculated as a coefficient of the sum of investment costs and a coefficient equal to 2:

³ Шальнева В.В., Блажевич О.Г. Бизнес-план реализации инвестиционного проекта // Научный вестник: финансы, банки, инвестиции. №3 (48), 2019. - С. 84.

$$ARR = \frac{\sum_{t=1}^T CF_t/T}{\sum_{t=1}^T I_t/2} \times T$$

If the project involves a residual or salvage value, its estimated volume should be excluded from the volume of capital investments:

$$ARR = \frac{\sum_{t=1}^T CF_t/T}{(\sum_{t=1}^T I_t - LC)/2} \times T$$

Where LC is the residual (liquidation) value of investments, soums.

The obtained ARR value is evaluated by comparison with the target index or the minimum acceptable index. Projects with ARR value above the target or acceptable level are accepted for implementation.

The statistical methods we have reviewed ignore the change in the value of money over time and do not take into account the cost of capital, as mentioned above.

In order to ensure the comparison of the expenses incurred in different periods, as well as the incoming cash flows of different years, it is necessary to implement the procedure of discounting them or, in other words, bringing them to a certain time. For a certain time, as a rule, the current (or zero) period is taken - the period when the project implementation began (t_0).

The discounting process is based on the operation of determining the present value of cash in terms of its future value:

$$PV = \frac{FV}{(1 + E)^t}$$

Where FV is the future cash flow;

PV - current (present) value of cash flow;

E - discount rate (rate of income), shares of units;

t - duration of the calculation period, years.

The future value of an investment is the amount that the investment made now will turn out after a certain time at a certain interest (discount) rate⁴.

⁴ ЮЗВОВИЧ Л.И. Инвестиции. Учебник. М.: Вильямс, 2016. с. 147.

The present value of the cash flow is the product of the future value and the discount factor, the general formula of which is:

$$a = \frac{1}{(1 + E)^t}$$

Where a is the discount coefficient, fractions of a unit;

E - discount rate (rate of income), shares of units;

t - duration of the calculation period, years.

Based on the above formula, the discount factor for the calculation step m is determined by the following formula:

$$a_m = \frac{1}{(1 + E)^{t_m - t_0}}$$

where a_m - m is the discount factor for the calculation step, a percentage of the unit;

E - discount rate (rate of income), shares of units;

t_m - end of step m ;

t_0 - shortening moment.

The discount rate is an exogenously determined economic indicator. The discount rate can be:

- commercial - determined taking into account the alternative effectiveness of the use of invested capital;
- social - describing the minimum social requirements for the project;
- budget - determined by the executive authorities, representing the effectiveness of the project for budgets of different levels;
- project participant - representing the efficiency of participation of various participants in the project.

The value of the discount factor must always be less than one, otherwise the money will be worth less today than in the future. In conclusion, we emphasize that by evaluating the considered efficiency indicators, the investor makes a conclusion about the feasibility of implementing a certain project, as well as giving priority to a particular project when there are alternatives.

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